

IMPROVE-HF RESEARCH COMMUNITY

NEWSLETTER

JANUARY 2026

PROJECT UPDATES

Focus of the systematic review

Our thematic analysis of discussions at the sandpit event (Sept 25) suggested a clear need to focus research on improving the early diagnosis of heart failure in primary care.

We are aware that other researchers are investigating screening, point-of-care testing and new pathways to improve early diagnosis. In our next phase of work, we will examine the evidence-base for existing primary-care interventions in a systematic review. The protocol for the review is published on [PROSPERO](#).

British Society of Heart Failure

We presented results of work package 3 at the British Society of Heart Failure Annual Meeting (20–21 Nov, London).

In this project, we showed that it is feasible to extract a large dataset of routinely-collected echo measurements from a health board and link it to other healthcare outcomes to improve heart failure research (see page 3).

Can you help us to share key messages of this work in your region?

National Cardiovascular Research Network

We presented results of the sandpit event (work package 1) and work package 3 at the National Cardiovascular Research Network event on 4 December.

New team members

Joining us in 2026 are:

- Nicky Heady - Research Officer
- Tim Driscoll - Statistician
- Iris Evans - Trial assistant and administrator

Welcome to the second edition of the IMPROVE-HF newsletter!

Since our last issue, we've been focusing on work package 2, drafting the protocol for our systematic review. The interventions and innovations we're exploring have been shaped by the insights and priorities provided by the attendees of the sandpit event in September. This ensures that any future proposed research programme reflects real-world challenges.

In this edition, you'll also find information about new team members, poster results from the sandpit event and data science work packages, and sign-posts to other heart failure research.

Not yet part of our research community? Scan the QR code or click the [link](#) to join.

WORK PACKAGE 1 POSTER

This poster summarises the results of work package 1. It was presented at the National Cardiovascular Research Network Event on the 4th December 2025.

How can we improve heart failure outcomes in Wales? Thematic analysis of the opportunities for collaborative health-service research.

Aimee Drane^{1,2}, Jodie Millard¹, Carys Jones^{1,2}, Delyth Rucarean², Hayley Taylor², Kerys Thomas², Joshua Lau², Elizabeth Ellins¹, Roderic Ashley³, Carol Barrett³, Elizabeth Neve³, Julie Hepburn³, Hameed Khan³, Jonathan Williams³, Ben Dicken², Parin Shah², Geraint Jenkins² and Emma Rees^{1,2}

(¹Swansea University, ²Swansea Bay University Health Board, ³Public Contributor)

Background

In Wales, heart failure (HF) is typically diagnosed late, often during hospital admission, and there is variation in clinical outcomes across the health boards.

The IMPROVE-HF project seeks to develop a pan-Wales programme of research to reduce variation in care and improve outcomes.

In the first of four work packages, we held a sandpit event with a wide range of interested groups to:

- 1 Identify service challenges and factors leading to poor HF outcomes in Wales.
- 2 Document ideas for innovation and service-based interventions to improve care.
- 3 Prioritise the type of intervention and outcome measures to be evaluated in a systematic review prior to use in a research programme.

Methods

We invited a range of healthcare professionals, researchers, public contributors and third sector representatives to attend a sandpit event to discuss HF services and outcomes in Wales.

Group activities were used to identify:

1. Factors affecting HF outcomes (Ishikawa diagram and prioritisation matrix).
2. Innovative solutions to improve outcomes (opportunity mapping and idea pitching).

Results

Thematic analysis :

Opportunities for service-based interventions to improve outcomes

Person at risk of HF

Better outcomes

Key findings

- 1 There is variation in services across Wales. One of the biggest challenges is providing early diagnosis in primary care settings.
- 2 Proposed interventions recognised the need to embrace prevention, multi-professional working and new technology (including AI).
- 3 In the next phase of work, the group has decided to evaluate the evidence for service-based interventions to improve case-finding and early diagnosis.

Conclusion

Meaningful engagement with healthcare providers, researchers, public contributors and third sector organisations enabled us to:

- Frame the current challenges in HF care.
- Prioritise the interventions which are most likely to impact outcomes in Wales.

Next Steps.....

- Disseminate the findings to the IMPROVE-HF network, Health Board leaders, third sector representatives and the public.
- Improve opportunities for those in Betsi Cadwaladr and Powys to engage with our work.
- Perform a systematic review and meta-analysis of the effectiveness of existing interventions which aim to find individuals with HF and accelerate diagnosis.
- Determine whether to adopt, adapt or develop new service-based interventions for a pan-Wales HF research programme.

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Sign up to our IMPROVE_HF research community for updates on developing a HF research programme in Wales.

WORK PACKAGE 3 POSTER

This poster summarises the results of work package 3. It was presented at the British Society of Heart Failure Annual Meeting, 20-21 November 2025.

Improving heart failure research at a population level by linking routinely collected echo measurements with electronic health record data: A feasibility study in Wales.

Aimee Drane^{1,2}, Victoria Best¹, Stephen Morris², Elizabeth Ellins¹, Ben Dicken², Adrian Ionescu², Emma Rees^{1,2}
on behalf of the IMPROVE-HF research group

¹Swansea University, ²Swansea Bay University Health Board

Background

Researchers can conduct population level research by accessing anonymised, linked electronic health record (EHR) within the SAIL Databank, but detailed echocardiographic (echo) data are not available. Our previous mapping of heart failure (HF) pathway and outcomes in Wales highlighted challenges in identifying whether echo had occurred, HF subtype or severity.

We propose incorporating echo measurements into the SAIL Databank (without images or free text) to enhance HF research at scale.

Aims:

- 1 Test feasibility of extracting routinely collected echo measurements and linkage to EHR data within SAIL Databank.
- 2 Examine completion rates of HF core echo measurements.
- 3 Compare counts of echo using (i) standard EHR data and (ii) new measurement dataset, for those with a diagnosis of HF.

Methods

Results

Completion rates for core echo measurements (%)

LVIDd: Left ventricle internal dimension, diastole. LVIDs: Left ventricle internal dimension, systole. LVMi: Left ventricle mass indexed for body surface area. EF: Ejection fraction. LAV: Left atrial volume

Heart failure sub-group

Key findings

- 1 Linking routine echo measurements with EHR is feasible and scalable across multiple hospitals in a region.
- 2 There were low completion rates of core HF measurements in structured database fields prior to 2023.
- 3 Using standard EHR data, the number of echoes in the HF pathway was under-counted. Incorporation of echo measurement data doubled the visibility of echoes.

Next steps

Disseminate findings to Health Boards across Wales and explore opinions on whether this work could be scaled up from regional to national level.

Encourage all echocardiographers to use structured measurement fields in reporting (not solely free-text). This is vital if measurements are to be used in research.

Perform detailed analysis of linked data for those with HF and echo from 2023-2024 to examine 'added value' of incorporating echo measurements into population level research.

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Research Team Spotlight

Kerys Thomas

Kerys Thomas is an Advanced Heart Failure Pharmacist within the Community Heart Failure Team at Swansea Bay University Health Board. Kerys is passionate about advancing heart failure services in the community and has led on developing a Heart Failure Annual Review Service in Swansea Bay and setting up a Rapid Optimisation Clinic, which improves access to evidence-based treatments.

“Our service in Swansea is unusual being Nurse- and Pharmacist-led, supported by health care support workers and an administrative team. We collaborate closely with our hospital and primary care colleagues to deliver specialist care for people with a diagnosis of heart failure.

A multi-disciplinary approach brings significant benefits. Nurses and pharmacists bring different skills, knowledge and perspectives to the service. As pharmacists, we have been instrumental in improving access to evidenced based medicines across the health board through development of new prescribing clinics, formulary updates, and education initiatives.

We provide a range of clinics across the health board with pharmacist prescribers supporting the rapid optimisation of heart failure treatments. We are a pilot site for the implementation of STRONG HF which aims to fully optimise treatment for patients recently hospitalised with heart failure within a few weeks of referral.

Involvement in IMPROVE-HF has been incredibly interesting. It has provided a forum offering insight into service provision across Wales and helping to address gaps and variation. It's been great to be involved; the group has created an environment where all are encouraged to contribute and offered the opportunity to develop their understanding of the world of research.”

Latest Advances in Heart Failure Research

Using routinely collected health record data for the earlier detection of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction: FIND-HFpEF

This paper outlines why earlier identification of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) remains challenging and how routinely collected electronic health records (EHRs) could help bridge that gap. HFpEF is common, often diagnosed late and poorly captured within current coding systems, limiting accurate epidemiology and timely care. The FIND-HFpEF study aims to use linked UK primary and secondary care data to better classify HFpEF, quantify its true burden and develop prediction algorithms that can flag high-risk or undiagnosed individuals directly within EHR systems. The authors argue that scalable, data-driven detection could support earlier diagnosis, guide service planning and reduce the long-term clinical impact of HFpEF.

Use of artificial intelligence for detecting left ventricular dysfunction and predicting incident heart failure risk

This review examines how artificial intelligence could transform early detection of heart failure, especially in people with silent or subclinical dysfunction. Drawing on nearly 1,000 studies, it highlights AI models that analyse electronic health records, ECGs and echocardiography to identify risk more accurately than traditional tools. Together, these advances enable a structured, multi-step screening pathway using AI-driven EHR analysis, ECG, biomarkers, and echocardiography, improving early identification, focusing resources on higher-risk individuals, and supporting more timely, targeted preventive care.

